

COMMENTARY

On a chart being a chart of *two or more events simultaneously*, and on whether a specific matter should be judged under a *deterministic* or a *free will* approach

- **A CHART BEING A CHART OF TWO OR MORE EVENTS**

Any chart can be—and actually is—a chart of over 1,000 events (minimum) in that location on Earth for which said chart was or is going to be drafted, which is why a competition based on **who can guess** what a given astrology is about can only be absurd. Moreover, it would appear to show very little understanding about astrology or how it works, as every few minutes in a specific location on Earth a child is born and a person dies or is killed, a document is signed and trips, journeys, and work shifts begin, not to mention land and air traffic collisions, among many other events. How, then, is a competent astrologer to distinguish the subject-matter of any given chart, which is the same as asking how can a competent physician determine the patient or person to which any given laboratory results (e.g. bloodwork) correspond? He cannot.

If we were to insist on promoting a match whereby the person who determines which chart corresponds to which event first wins the match, we would have—or it would be wise—to employ any two charts of two events of the **same nature** (e.g. birth, murder, employment, journey) with specific distinctions. In sum, a context. We are not to tell the candidates that one chart corresponds to a love date and the other one to a murder, for a murder may have been executed with no violence at all and a love date may have ended badly, in which case it would be the *murder chart* that would show platonic or pleasurable (or pharmacological) traits¹ [1] and the *love date chart* violent or otherwise conflicting clues or indications. Thus, it may be convenient to choose two charts of two events on the same subject and ask which of the two presented the **characteristics** provided. Say, two charts of two job offers in order to determine which one was or will be more profitable² [2]. Or two charts of two murders and determine which of the two was consumed with poison or drugs, and

¹ Pisces, Venus, and/or Neptune may be involved. Neptune and Pisces are closely related to substances or drugs, poison, and alcohol.

² One may even go as far as to provide what type of job it is in order to determine the limit of its potential or its initial potential, like, say, a Waiter or a Valet job offer versus an Insurance Broker job offer.

which with a firearm. Or two charts of two famous individuals to determine which one is the actor and which the scientist, or which one the painter and which the writer.

The exercise described above would prove the analytical ability or skill of the astrologer in question, that is, his or her ability to discern or decipher the astrological language, his or her aptitude or talent as a professional interpreter/delineator³ [3].

Every nonexact, although empirical science or discipline requires context, naturally. Take, for example, medicine and psychiatry, forensic psychology and law, among others. Although mathematics, physics or astrophysics, and even chemistry constitute the very being of astrology, **astrological assessments** (i.e. chart delineation) are not necessarily mathematical nor chemical, as neither necessarily are medical assessments despite biology, chemistry, and physics constituting the very being of medicine. In other words, diagnoses and prognoses in both astrology and medicine (including psychiatry and forensic psychology) are nonexact judgments or interpretations of exact information. In medicine, blood types and volumes, MRIs, and many, if not all lab results constitute exact information. In astrology, also the Sun's or Mercury's or Saturn's ecliptic and house positions as well as their aspectual relationships with other members of our solar system as seen from Earth, or the degree of an event's ascending sign.

Because of this, **contextual requirements** have nothing to do with the skill or aptitude of the practising professional, but with the nature of the trade itself. Knowing whether a chart is of a man or of a woman, of a country or of an employment, among other fundamental characteristics for interpretation purposes, is context. In the case of employment and countries, one must know what the employment is about and whether the country belongs to the first or the third world. Say, a physician, no matter how great he or she may be, cannot be a competent one without inquiring about the patient's medical history and that of their family. Neither can the best lawyer. The latter needs to learn all the facts and their characteristics before even imagining the angle or the path of his defense or prosecution, which is why "discovery" is fundamental in criminal proceedings (i.e. failure to disclose possession

³ In law and in medicine, one may be a great law professor and an awful litigant, or vice versa, as well as a great physiotherapist and an awful surgeon, or vice versa. Likewise, in astrology, an astrologer may be great at delineation and awful at theory and/or history of astrology, or vice versa (which has always been the trend).

of certain information—abuse of the discovery process—can result in sanctions from the court).

Although we do practise a science by all accounts, it is a nonexact one nonetheless⁴ [4], i.e., a *scientific art* or an *artistic science*, like the ones aforementioned (even though astrology is a natural science, as Ptolemy and the Arabs thought it to be). I, for my part, believe to have been more competent to provide legal advise (from an astrological standpoint) to those who have needed it because I have been provided with the facts of the case and the parties to the dispute in order to identify them in the chart without mistaking them for someone else, thereby being able to shed light on their apparent intentions (beyond what's obvious to the court) in accordance with house-sign-planetary composition or relationships⁵ [5].

Both students and professional aspirants to a “death match”, then, should or may test their skills this way.

- **DETERMINISTIC VERSUS A FREE WILL APPROACH OR JUDGEMENT**

Any self-respected philosopher, astrologer, and/or geneticist knows that **knowledge** broadens or amplifies **free will**, whereas **ignorance** reduces or diminishes it, that is, enhances or otherwise enforces (genetic/astrological) **determinism**. This can be verified empirically, easily so with any given medical or employment example of real life. Take an individual with a genetic or an astrological predisposition to contract certain types of cancer, but that in knowing so thanks to assessments conducted by a competent physician and/or astrologer, now has been provided with specific recommendations as to either avoid it or reduce its probabilities considerably, just as a victim of a heist, robbery, or murder may become aware of the fact thanks to the

⁴ That is to say, a science whose diagnoses and prognoses are to be nurtured by or with multiple variables in order to be precise (i.e. it is not independent, like say, mathematics). Whereas a physician may determine the cause of a lumbar pain *exactly* by conducting an MRI, a physiotherapist may determine it *empirically* by conducting multiple observations and drawing information from answers to multiple questions. The more variables are considered or acknowledged, the more precise any diagnosis or prognosis (as in meteorology, another nonexact science because of the many variables at stake, magnetic fields included).

⁵ One may, however, be able to do this vice versa, that is, to ask if there would be someone who fits or may fit the description or that would be doing something as described in the chart so that we can learn who is or may be involved in the judicial process (i.e. who we are looking at) beyond the obvious parties to the lawsuit/case.

work of the police (or of the secret service, upon the case) and avoid it or neutralize it thereby⁶ [6]. Take too the example of an individual who has not been able to decide between two good job offers due to a lack of specific knowledge concerning schedules, wages after taxes, and the person to whom he or she will report, among other variables. It should be noted: the more information the individual possesses about the two jobs the more empowered he or she will become in order to decide correctly or reasonably (with peace of mind, at least).

Only when certain tendencies are extremely genetically or astrologically powerful, there is very little one may do to overcome them, though much to embrace them. When then, should we consider a tendency (as per described in the astrography) difficult or easy to overcome? This would be considered relatively simple as well. If, say, an individual presented the ruler of its ASC lodged in the 8th House holding a square with both Saturn and Mars in Leo and an opposition to either Uranus or Neptuno or Pluto in the 2nd House, a tendency to overcome physical, health, and/or metabolic issues (even premature death) may be difficult, if not impossible to overcome. If, say, an individual presented the ruler of its ASC lodged in the 8th House holding a square with Saturn conjunct Jupiter and/or Venus in Leo and an opposition with the Moon in Taurus in the 2nd House, a tendency to overcome physical, health, and/or metabolic issues (even premature death) may be less difficult, if not easy to overcome.

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⁶ Whether an observation arises from genetic rather than environmental factors (e.g. someone's tendency to contract a certain disease) or from environmental rather than genetic factors (e.g. someone's tendency to lead an unemployed life) is key. In the first case, the environment exerts little influence (although it can). In the second, genes exert little influence (although they can). Thus, in the former case, nutritional instructions, among others, will or are to be provided, whereas, in the latter, recommendations on behavioural patterns plus specific cities or countries wherein one would exhibit a tendency to live most pleasantly or successfully. Please see our *Commentary on Astrology according to Epigenetics* (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8210414>), commonly referred as *Ptolemy's Thought Experiment?*